

A Proof of Snell's Law

Using the Circumcircle and the Alternate Segment Theorem

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Overview

This proof of Snell's Law makes use of the following results and definitions:

1. Laws of reflection
2. Defining refractive index as the velocity ratio between the incident ray and the refracted ray
3. Triangular representation of vectors (the vector here being velocity)
4. Circumcircles of triangles and their tangents
5. The alternate segment theorem
6. The sine rule

$$n = V_1 / V_2$$

Figure 1: The incident ray IG meets the interface at G and refracts along GE .

Setting Up the Construction

We begin with the incident ray of light IG and the refracted ray GE . The horizontal line represents the interface between the two media.

From the principle of reflection, the reflected ray makes the same angle with the normal as the incident ray. We take this reflected ray, HG , to have velocity V_1 , and the refracted ray GE to have velocity V_2 .

Together these rays form a triangle, GHE . We construct its circumcircle.

This construction allows the triangle's angles to be related to the tangent at G , creating a geometric link between the velocity directions and the angles of incidence and refraction.

The horizontal interface therefore acts as a tangent to the circumcircle at G, allowing the tangent–chord relationship to be applied.

Figure 2: Triangle GHE and its circumcircle, tangent to the interface at G.

Applying the Alternate Segment Theorem

By the alternate segment theorem:

- The angle that HG (velocity V_1) makes with the normal is the angle of incidence, i . This angle is equal to $\angle GEH$.
- The angle that GE (velocity V_2) makes with the normal is the angle of refraction, r . This angle is equal to $\angle GHE$.

Deductions

The angle that HG makes with the horizontal is $(90 - i)^\circ$, and the angle that GE makes with the horizontal is $(90 - r)^\circ$.

It follows that:

$$\angle EGH = 180^\circ - (i + r)$$

As a check, the three angles of triangle GHE should sum to 180° :

$$\angle GEH + \angle GHE + \angle EGH = i + r + [180^\circ - (i + r)] = 180^\circ \checkmark$$

Applying the Sine Rule

Since GH and GE are vector representations of the velocities V_1 and V_2 drawn to the same scale, their lengths are proportional to their magnitudes. And treating them as sides of a triangle using sine's rule, We deduce :

$$V_1 / \sin i = V_2 / \sin r$$

Rearranging:

$$n = V_1 / V_2 = \sin i / \sin r$$

This recovers Snell's Law: **$n = \sin i / \sin r$** , derived purely from the geometry of reflection, the circumcircle of triangle GHE, the alternate segment theorem, and the sine rule.